

Dr. R.K.B. Law College

Newsletter

Volume 1 Issue II
(July – December 2023)

Editor: Dr. Jayanta Boruah

From the Principal Desk Editorial

With great pleasure and immense pride we welcome you to the 2nd edition of the Volume I of the Newsletter of Dr Rohini Kanta Barua Law College, Dibrugarh. Laws of the land of a country are the medicine for the existing societal evils. Thus, a law college has tremendous responsibilities while preparing students for their professional field. The effort of our college in this regard has been reflected in this 2nd edition of the Newsletter. We anticipate your best regards in all our efforts in our upcoming days too.

With regards
Dr Gautomi Dutta
Principal
Dr R. K. B. Law College, Dibrugarh

From the Desk of IQAC
Coordinator

Dear Readers

The 2nd Edition of the Newsletter reflects the collaborative efforts of our entire college community and highlights the diverse achievements, events and initiatives that have taken place over the previous year. It provides a platform to celebrate the accomplishments of our students and faculty and keep everyone informed about the events and opportunities. The dedication and enthusiasm of the entire college community have truly made this newsletter a reflection of the spirit and excellence of our prestigious institution. I encourage all faculty, staff and students to read the newsletter and share it with others. Let us continue to support and promote the wonderful work happening within our college community.

With regards
Mrs. Shilpi Gupta
Coordinator, IQAC
Dr. R.K.B. Law College, Dibrugarh, Assam

As we embark upon the second issue of our esteemed Dr. R.K.B. Law College Newsletter, it is imperative to reflect on the strides we've made and the path that lies ahead. Our institution, under the visionary leadership of distinguished faculties, continues to stand as a beacon of legal education, nurturing the minds of future legal luminaries.

In the past months, we've witnessed an unwavering commitment to academic excellence and holistic development. From rigorous classroom discussions to engaging in outreaching activities including excursion and social awareness programmes, every facet of our students' journey has been meticulously crafted to instil in them a deep understanding of education and its implications in society. Moreover, our distinguished faculty members have played a pivotal role in shaping the intellectual landscape of our institution. Their dedication to scholarship and mentorship has not only enriched the academic experience but has also inspired countless students to strive for greatness. This issue reflects some of such achievements made in the last 6 months

Dr. Jayanta Boruah
Editor

Major Headings at a Glance

- National Article Writing Competition 2023
- Appointment for New Faculties
- Orientation Programme for Teachers of Law
- Orientation cum Interview Programme
- Grand Inauguration of BBA.II.B. Course
- Mental Health Awareness Programme conducted by Vartaman Care Network Foundation
- Release of Annual Students' Magazine and International Journal
- Observance of Constitution Day
- Teachers' Day Celebration and Farewell to the Last Year Students of the College
- Moot Court Training Programme
- Celebration of Alumni Get Together Congrego
- Interview Session with Sr, AOR Vijay Hansaria
- Street Play on Non-Violence
- Mock Interview by Placement Cell
- MoU with DHSK College
- Online FDPs on Human Rights and Research Methodology

National Article Writing Competition 2023

July 19, 2023: A National Article Writing Competition was launched with exciting cash prizes for the winners. It was opened for all students of law and submissions were to be made online. The theme of the competition was based on contemporary developments in Intellectual Property and Business Law Affairs especially with respect to global developments.

The competition received a huge response from across the country and after a three-phased review of all the submissions, Miss Tejaswini Kaushal from Ram Manohar Lahiya National Law University received the First Position; Miss. Shruti Kukreti from Fairfield Institute of Management and Technology received the Second Position, and Mrs. Shramin Mohammad Anwar Sheikh from Bar Council of Goa and Maharashtra received the Third Position

respectively. They were provided with monetary awards through online payments and the top 10 quality papers were published in the First Volume of Annual International Journal of Intellectual Property and Corporate Affairs (AIJPCA), an annual international journal jointly published by Dr. R.K.B. Law College, Nowgong Law College and Aequitas Victoria Foundation. Some papers were also published in the Annual Students Magazine of the college.

National Article Writing Competition,
Prizes worth INR: 5,000,
No Registration Charges,
Register by July 31, 2023

Organized by
Dr R.K.B. Law College,
Dibrugarh, Assam

Advertisement for Appointment of New Faculty

July 25, 2023: An advertisement was issued for recruitment against the vacancy of an Assistant Professor in Management through w.e.f RKBLC/Advt/2023/134. Candidates with UGC NET/SLET/Ph.D. was to be preferred. The interview was conducted subsequently and on July 31st, 2023, Dr Deepankar Bhattacharjee was appointed as the new

Assistant Professor in Management for the newly launched BBA.LL.B. Course.

Dr Deepankar Bhattacharjee

Appointment of Visiting Faculties

July 26, 2023: In addition, 2 Visiting Faculties were also appointed namely Dr Mahesh Jain and Mr Srimanta Bordoloi to assist in the teaching of BBA.LL.B Course. These appointments were to be effective from August 07, 2023, once the new academic session resumes.

In total 3 faculties were appointed to begin with the new course of 5 years BBA.LL.B. In addition, the Post of the Faculty of English subject, Mrs. Ritimoni Sarmah was also regularized.

Orientation Programme for Teachers of Law

July 30, 2023: Dr. R.K.B. Law College in association with the Nowgong Law College organized an Orientation Programme for Teachers of Law from July 28 to 30 2023. The programme was organized in hybrid mode where it was physically hosted at the college premises of Nowgong Law College. The programme covered significant topics of law including Management and Personality Development; Orientation in Jurisprudence; Orientation in Constitutional

Law; Mental and Physical Health; Orientation in Business Law; and Orientation in Criminal Law. Resource Persons like Prof. Avani Bhagawati; Prof. R.C. Barpatragohain; Prof. Subhram Rajkhowa; Dr Aparajita Baruah; Dr Saumya Shankar Chowdhury; Sri Angshuman Bora, Sri Surajit Bharali, and Sri Parswa JD Nair graced the occasion. Around 30 participants from different law colleges of Assam participated along with the Faculties of both the institutions.

Orientation Cum Interactive Programme

August 07, 2023: The Anti-Ragging Squad and Committee of Dr. R.K.B. Law College organized an Orientation cum Interactive Programme to welcome and get introduced to the newly enrolled students at the beginning of the academic

Extension of Free Legal Aid from Nyayasharathi

August 08, 2023: The Nyayasharathi, the Legal Aid Cell of the College has provided a free legal advice to an middle-aged local person on the matter of attorney. Senior Advocate of Dibrugarh Bar Association and Former Vice Principal of the College advised the person in the Legal Aid Chamber of the College in the presence of college students.

Release of the Inaugural Issue of the Dr. R.K.B. Law College Newsletter

August 14, 2023: During the Grand Inauguration Programme of the 5 years BBA.LL.B. Course of the college, the Chief Guest of Honor, the Hon'ble Vice Chancellor of Dibrugarh University in the presence of other dignitaries inaugurated the First Issue of the Inaugural Volume of the Dr. R.K.B. Law College Newsletter.

Independence Day Celebration

August 15, 2023: On August 15, 2023, the college celebrated the independence day of India by hoisting the National Flag in the presence of both Teaching and Non-teaching Staff as well as students. The occasion was even more special due to the nation-wide celebration of Azadi Ka Amrit Mahatsov

session. The new students from both 3 years LL.B. Course and 5 years BBA.LL.B. Course were invited and were allowed to introduce themselves and to share their opinions behind choosing law as a career and to prefer the institution to advance in their career. The senior students were also asked to interact with the new students. The main motive behind the event was to create an interactive platform for both the senior and the newly enrolled students so that chances for ragging could be reduced to the possible extent. This initiative was also adopted by the college authority to inform the students about the consequences of ragging and how seriously the Anti-Ragging squad of the college will deal if any student is found engaged with such activities. The event was moderated by Mr. Jayanta Boruah and concluded with group photographs

Grand Inauguration of BBA.LL.B. Course

August 14, 2023: The beginning of the new academic session was marked with great enthusiasm for the college since for the college successfully secured approval for the 5 years BBA.LL.B. Course from the Bar Council of India. And as a consequent to such approval admissions for the said course was initiated and successfully the first batch of the course was admitted In the college. As a result, on August 14, 2023, the college authority organized a grand inauguration programme of the 5 years BBA.LL.B. course. The event was highly enlightened with the presence of the Hon'ble Vice Chancellor of Dibrugarh University, Prof. (Dr.) Jiten Hazarika as the Chief Guest of Honor. He in his special address encouraged the newly enrolled students and appreciated the entire college authority for such a great achievement. He raised his expectation from the institution and extended his best regards for the future endeavours. The event got more auspicious with the presence of the President of the Governing Body of the College, Dr. Prakash Barooah who also expressed his emotions on the said occasion. The event was brightened up by a number of mesmerizing performances by the new students who with the exceptional talent glorified the audience. It was finally concluded with the extension of Formal Vote of Thanks by Dr. Deepankar Bhattacharya. The proceeding of the event was also published in a couple of local dailies the next day.

Soil Testing within the Campus

August 18, 2023: To accomplish the requirement of Annual Green Audit Report of the college and also government imposed regulations on construction of new building, a soil testing drive was done within the campus through recognized authority. It was done under the supervision of the Eco-sense Club of the college at the presence of Dr. Bijeta Chetry and Dr. Jayanta Boruah. The soil testing was done with the objective of knowing the strength of the soil for construction of any structure within the geographical limits of the college campus. Further the testing was necessary to complete the Green Audit Report where assessment of the quality of the soil is required as a matter of Audit.

Alumni Talk Series – II on Techniques of Mediation for Students

August 18, 2023: The Alumni Association of Dr. R.K.B. Law College organized the second talk series on the topic “Techniques of Mediation” for the students of LL.B. 5th Semester and LL.B. 3rd Semester. The session was chaired by Advocate Jupindar Kaur who is a trainer of mediation and also a member of Juvenile Justice Board. She is an alumni of the college and hence delivered an enlightening session on the said topic. The event was also co-chaired by Sr. Advocate S.C. Goswami who is also a Senior Lecturer of the college entrusted with the responsibility of teaching the subject of Alternative Dispute Resolution to the students.

Mental Health Awareness Programme conducted by Vartaman Care Network Foundation

August 18, 2023: The Placement Cell of Dr. Rohini Kanta Barua Law College, Dibrugarh, Assam in association with Vartamaan Care Network Foundation organized a workshop on the subject of Mental Health Awareness. The main objective of the event was to enable the students to be free for better careers in the legal profession. The workshop was chaired by three trained Psychologists named: Chetna Singhania, Stawani Bhuyan, and Bhagyashree Gogoi. They initially spoke on stress, causes of stress, and

consequences of stress specifically in students’ lives. Subsequently, they interacted with the students to understand their problems including their emotions and sentiments on

various social evils and personal attacks. Subsequently, Chetna Singhania gave instructions on how to get relief from stress. Further, they established individual communication with students for one-to-one training and counseling. The workshop was moderated by Dr. Jayanta Boruah,

Coordinator, Placement Cell, and finally the formal vote of thanks was delivered by Dr. Deepankar Bhattacharjee, Assistant Professor, Dr. R.K.B. Law College.

Call for Book Chapters

August 19, 2023: A Call for Chapters was released at the national level for publication of an ISBN Book in the year 2024. The theme for the book was decided to be based on

Transformation of Traditional Legal Institutions for the Post-Sustainable Development World. Dr. Dhrubajyoti Das, Associate Professor of Cotton University was approached to become one of the external editors of the book and to guide the publication procedure..

Call for Contributions to Fortiori Reflecto Botanical Audit for the Green Audit Report

August 20, 2023: A Call for Contributions to Fortiori Reflecto Volume 1 (2023) was released at the national platform through online. The Call was for receiving contributions from across the country for publishing an annual students' magazine of the college by the end of 2023.

August 20, 2023: The final audit of the different plant species within the campus was completed for the Annual Green Audit Report of the College. the audit was supported by Ramdev Rai, Akash Kumar Razak and Prasenjeet Nath under the supervision of Dr Jayanta Boruah.

Biennial Conference of Dibrugarh Senior Citizens' Council

September 03 2023: The Senior Citizens' Council of Dibrugarh organized its biennial conference that is organized once in every two years in respect and honour for the contributions made by the Senior Citizens of the locality. In this conference many dignitaries including the Former Vice Chancellor of Dibrugarh University were present. Their presence made the occasion more enlightening and delightful for the audience. In the same event two books authored by Senior Citizens were released and four Senior Citizens were appreciated and awarded with letters of appreciation for their valuable contributions towards the society.

Teachers' Day Celebration

September 05, 2023: The students union with the assistance of all the students of the college organized an event in honour of the teachers of the college on the birth anniversary of Sarvepalli Radhakrishnan. The college authority also joined the event to show respect to one of the distinguished Teacher and Novelist from Dibrugarh, Dr Bharati Dutta. The event was hosted jointly by Bandana Hazarika in Assamese and Satyakam Sarma in English. It began with the felicitation of the Guest of Honour and subsequently the cake cutting ceremony followed. The students showed their devotion to

their teachers through different performances and gifts.

Farewell to the Last-Year Students of the College

September 05, 2023: The Teachers' Day celebration was followed by the Anajori programme where the last-year students were given farewell and the new batches were welcomed to the institution. The present senior-batch students use to organize the event every year and this year also the event was successfully organized. Each student from the last-year final batch who was present during the event in person was felicitated by the senior students through the faculty members individually. A few last-year students also expressed their emotions on mike.

Freshmen Social Day

September 05, 2023: The Farewell ceremony was followed by the General Freshers for the new batches of students of the college. The event was glorified by different entertaining performances demonstrated by both the new and old students. At the end of the event, Mr and Ms Fresher were selected by the Judges and awarded by the students union members. The event ended with cultural performances.

Moot Court Training Programme

September 08, 2023: The Moot Court Society of Dr. R.K.B. Law College organized a Moot Court Training Programme to enhance the skill of the students in Trial Advocacy and Mooting. Mr Tawhid Alom Laskar, Advocate of Gauhati High Court was invited as the Resource Person. He possesses immense experience in the field of Moot Court and Debate with the record of winning 35 Debate Competitions across the country and a number of Moot

Court Titles. He is also an alumni of NLU Assam and the Debating Secretary of NUL Assam Students Bar Association. The Resource Person was co-chaired by Sr. Advocate cum Lecturer Mr S.C. Goswami. The session was attended by the students of LL.B. 3rd Semester and LL.B. 5th Semester. The session was fruitful for the students and they demanded for future interaction with the Resource Person. The event was concluded with the Formal Vote of Thanks.

Celebration of the First Alumni Get Together: Congrego

September 09, 2023: The Alumni Association of Dr. R.K.B. Law College organized a Get Together in the form of Congrego as an interactive platform for the Alumnis. The meeting was hosted by Veteran Teacher Smt. Rina Rani Bora. The local MLA Mr Prasanta Phukan attended the meeting as the Chief Guest of Honor. Almost 100 alumni from across the country attended the meeting and shared their opinions and emotions attached with the college. The event initiated with the lighting of the lamp ceremony. A number of cultural events followed the address of the Guest of Honour. The most entertaining cultural event was the Mime Act that was performed for the first time in the college by the students.

Foundation of the College Main Gate

on the same occasion, the main gate of the college was decided to be renovated by the alumni association for which the foundation was laid down.

Interview Session with Advocate on Record Vijay Hansaria

September 09, 2023: An online interview session was organized by the Placement Cell of Dr. Rohini Kanta Barua Law College, Dibrugarh, Assam with Senior Advocate on

Record Mr. Vijay Hansaria who is the first Advocate on Record from North-East India. He was joined by his junior Ms. Kavya Jhavar who was awarded Gold Medal for her securing state highest marks in her LL.B. from the Former President of India Mr. Ramnath Kovind. The interview was based on the topic Opportunities for Becoming an Advocate on Record for the Students from North-Eastern India.

During the interview Mr. Hansaria addressed the vital issues and challenges in the profession of Advocate on Record especially those that require technical knowledge. He however explained in detailed about the opportunities for north-east students in this profession and suggested to adopt technology in their approach. He highlighted that at present there is no such differences between North-East India and mainland India and even drafting of Gauhati High Court is much better than those of other High Courts from rest of India. He encouraged all the students to pursue their internship under advocates that can provide them with quality time.

The interview was attended by students from LLB. and BBA.LL. First Semesters. It was moderated by Ms. Basuri Poddar, LLM student from National Law University Bhopal. The event was finally concluded with questions from the students attending the session and a formal vote of

thanks by Mr. Jayanta Boruah, Faculty Coordinator of the Placement Cell.

Falicitation of Smt. Anushka Tarangini Baruah

September 09, 2023: An event in the name of Akanshya was organized by a local artist association within the premises of the college in the evening of September 09, 2023 to falicitate a young talented singer of Assam Smt. Anushka Tarangini Baruah, who became nationally popular through her amazing vocal performance. The event was made more entertaining through a number of cultural performances. The event became an example of inspiration for aspiring talented artists of the land.

Plantation Drive: Amrit Bikhya Rupayan

September 15, 2023: The college initiated a plantation drive within its campus. The drive was initiated following the state government

instructions for implementing the mission Amrit Bikhya Rupayan. 100 saplings were provided to the college by the Forest Department out of which 15 saplings were planted within the campus by the students of the college and the remaining saplings were distributed among the local institutions located nearby.

Installation of Solar Lights in the College Campus

September 16, 2023: Solar Lights were installed within the college campus as a part of green initiative of the college

and also to reduce the electricity expenses. 2 solar lights were provided by the Municipality on a written request made by the Principal. The Municipality Warden issued 2 solar lights for the college that were installed under the supervision of the Eco-sense Club of the college.

Street Play on Non-Violence

October 01, 2023: Dr. R.K.B. Law College and the District Legal Services Authority, Dibrugarh together organized a legal awareness campaign on the occasion of non-violence day. A street play was performed by the students of the college as a part of the campaign. The theme of the play was based on non-violence. In a very short time, the students demonstrated different forms of violence like violence

against women, violence against children and violence against other marginalized sections. At the end the play also showed how law treats the offenders committing violence and what are the legal recourse available to prevent violence in the society. The street play was directed by Dr Jayanta Boruah and scripted by him and Sudipta Dutta jointly. The DLSA Secretary also gave an enlightening speech during the campaign.

The campaign was organized at Thana Chariali of Dibrugarh on the main road in front of a large public.

Mock Interview conducted by the Placement Cell

October 07, 2023: A mock interview was organized by the Placement Cell of Dr. Rohini Kanta Barua Law College, Dibrugarh, Assam. The expert for the session was Mr. Debojit Sharma, HR Manager of Hindustan Unilever Limited, who was referred by Mr. Srimanta Bordoloi, Guest Lecturer of Dr. R.K.B. Law College. Mr. Bordoloi himself also chaired the session as a resource person. The mock interview was organized for the

students of LLB. 3rd and 5th Semesters of the institution for enlightening them on job interviews and placement opportunities in campus selection processes.

The session was moderated by Mr. Jayanta Boruah, Assistant Professor of the institution. It was started with the welcome speech by the Principal followed by lectures from both the resource persons after they were been felicitated. It was subsequently followed by the mock interview of three students at a time. Even students of 1st Semester were also allowed to view the proceedings. At the end student's feedback were collected. The event was concluded by the formal vote of thanks by the faculty coordinator of the Placement Cell.

Dr. R.K.B. Law College Students Union General Election

October 14, 2023: The General Elections for the Dr. R.K.B. Law College Students' Union was to be held in the month of October 2023 for the academic session 2023 - 24. Accordingly election officer and other officials were

appointed and nominations were collected by the college authority for the different posts. However, after the scrutiny of the nomination papers, some of the candidates won the election without having any contestant while some of the

posts could not be filled due to non-availability of suitable candidates. Most of the candidates filing nominations were

found lacking the required percentage of attendance and hence their nominations were rejected by the Election Officer. Subsequently, the college authority decided to arrange a joint sitting with the students and to nominate candidates for the remaining posts of the union through open selection. The criteria was followed and Mr Akash Kumar Razak became the President and Mr Siddhant Jaishwal became the General Secretary of the Dr. R.K.B. Law College Students Union for the academic year 2023 - 24. The members were then made to administer the oath as per the Constitution of Dr. R.K.B. Law College.

College Excursion to Halflong

November 01, 2023: The college decided to arrange an excursion programme in the month of October and accordingly it was arranged from November 01, 2023 onwards to

Halflong, Dima Hasao district of Assam. The trip was accompanied by the Principal, Dr Gautomi Dutta Bora, 2 Faculty Members including Dr Bijeta Chetry and Dr Jayanta Boruah, 6 students and the children of Dr Gautomi and Dr Bijeta. The trip started from Guwahati Railway Station through a Tourist Train to Halflong

Railway Station. On arrival at Halflong, several places were visited including ethnic village, local temples, parks, and lakes.

The excursion was a memorable experience for the ones who joined it. It allowed the group to have a close association with the nature and to cherish the hilly environment.

Observance of Legal Services Day

November 09, 2023: The Nyayasarathi of Dr. R.K.B. Law College in association with the District Legal Services Authority (DLSA), Dibrugarh organized an awareness programme on the occasion of National Legal Services Day on November 09, 2023. The

them of the programme was child labour. Considering the theme, Dhaman Higher Secondary School was selected for the awareness programme to reach students less than 18 years of age. The Principal of the School recommended the students from Class IX - XII to attend the session and made all the necessary arrangements.

On the part of DLSA, the Secretary went along with an Advocate who is also an alumni of Dr. R.K.B. Law College as Resource Persons. From the college, the Vice Principal of the College and Sr. Advocate, Satyabrata Sarma went as the Resource Person along with Dr Jayanta Boruah who joined the campaign as a moderator of the event. The event started with the formal welcome speech delivered by the Principal of Dhaman Higher Secondary School. Subsequently, all the resource persons gave their enlightening speech to generate awareness on the issues of child labour and their legal implications one by one in front of the students. However, the resource persons

also highlighted that even the teachers should have attended the meeting for more effective outcome. The school authority appreciated all the resource persons and the moderator concluded the interactive session by extending a Formal Vote of Thanks to all the resource persons and the participants and also appreciated the warm hospitality offered by the school.

Performance of A street Play

On the same occasion, a street play was performed by the students of the college depicting the issues of child labour and their legal consequences. The street play basically intended to highlight the reasons why child labour emerges in the remote

Concept was given by Dr Jayanta Boruah. At the end of the street play Sr. Advocate Satyabrata Sarma emphasized the modern challenges that children of contemporary age are facing, the legal remedies available and the reason why such awareness programme becomes

places like the one in which the school itself is located and what are the preventions that one should adopt. The street play was scripted by Mr. Sudipta Dutta while the Direction and

necessary to be conducted.

The entire event was later concluded by the elaboration of the importance of the assistance in legal matters that could be provided by Nyayasarthi, the Legal Aid Cell of the college and extension of Formal Vote of Thanks provided by Dr Jayanta Boruah.

Celebration of Diwali with Great Enthusiasm

November 10, 2023: The Students Union of the college decided to arrange for the celebration of Diwali within the campus and accordingly the members of the Union made all the necessary arrangements. The Teaching and Non-Teaching Staff of the college also made a significant contribution to the event and finally diwali was celebrated with great enthusiasm. The entire campus was decorated with tuni lights made in India and clay lamps were lighted for

decorating the main gate and the roadway to the admin building. A few students also blew crackers although in a limited amount. Children of Faculty members were also present who enjoyed the occasion with much delight. Light snacks were also arranged by the student members of the Union and music was played on the rhythm of which the students danced and celebrated the occasion.

Signing of MoU with D.H.S. Kanoi College, Dibrugarh, Assam

November 17, 2023: Dr. R.K.B. Law College and D.H.S.K College are both neighbouring colleges promoting higher education since decades within the area of Dibrugarh district. It was in the later half of the year 2023, that the heads of both the institutions decided to enter into a Memorandum of Understanding for promoting academic excellence in the near future and accordingly the MoU was signed on November 17, 2023. Most importantly, the MoU served a prolonged requirement of a field for Dr. R.K.B. Law College where students could play and develop extra-curricular sporting

events. On the other hand, it benefited the D.S.H.K. College in having an academic partner for promoting its various academic activities. In short, the MoU served the purposes of both the institutions and is expected that this MoU will help in promoting academic excellence throughout the region of Dibrugarh district. The Principal, IQAC Coordinator, Faculty Members and Students Union members of

Dr. R.K.B. Law College went to D.H.S.K College Conference Hall for signing the MoU where the Principal and other Faculty Members of D.H.S.K. College greeted them and signed the MoU on behalf of D.S.H.K. College.

Constitution Day Celebration with the D.H.S. Kanoi College

between both the institutions previously on November 17, 2023.

The event began with the ceremony of lighting of the lamp and paying tribute to Dr. B.R. Ambedkar. It was followed by an introductory speech presented by Dr. L. Doungel. The Principal of Dr. R.K.B. Law College delivered the welcome speech. It was then followed by the Reading of the Preamble by Mr. Siddhant Jaishwal, General Secretary of the Dr. R.K.B. Law College Students' Union and the Preamble was recited by the audience along with Jaishwal. The event was inaugurated by the Principal of DSHK College. The resource person Mr. Iqbal

November 25, 2023: The Department of Political Science of D.H.S.K College and Dr. Rohini Kanta Barua Law College jointly observed the Constitution Day at the college premises of Dr. R.K.B. Law College. The event was chaired by the Principals of both the colleges Dr. Sashi Kanta Saikia and Dr. Gautomi Dutta Bora respectively, the HOD of the Political Science Department of D.H.S.K College, Dr. L. Doungel and by Mr. Iqbal Ahmed, Senior Journalist and Former President of All Assam Journalist Forum. The theme of the event was Democracy, Constitution and Role of Media in India. The event was an outcome of a MOU signed

Ahmed spoke on the main theme of the event and beautifully highlighted all the important aspects of democracy, the Constitution of India and the Role of Media in maintaining the spirit of Constitutional Democracy in India. He initiated his speech by explaining the meaning and the types of democracy, freedom of speech and the concept of constitutional governance. He then highlighted that how media actually originated from the basic roots of communication. He even spoke on the aspects of verification of the authenticity of the news published or broadcasted by the media and the factors that influences the functioning of the journalists. He concluded his speech by explaining the newly emerging concept of 'Media Imperialism' and the conversion of 5Ws to 5Cs. Most notably during his speech he remarked that the American Constitution at a very early stage recognized the Freedom of Press but India being the world's largest

democracy has failed to recognize such a freedom yet in the Constitution that unfortunately causes obstacles in exercising such freedom by the Indian media.

His speech was followed by an interactive session where the students from both the institution participated and the deliberations of the resource persons made the session even more enlightening. Finally, the formal Vote of Thanks was delivered by Dr. Biraj Dutta, Assistant Professor, Department of Political Science, D.H.S.K

College. At last the event was concluded by the performance of the State Anthem by the students of Dr. R.K.B. Law College. The entire event was moderated by Dr. Jayanta Boruah, Assistant Professor, Dr. R.K.B. Law College. It was attended by the faculties of both the institutions and almost 100 students from both the institutions.

Book Release Event at D.H.S.K. College

November 26, 2023: A book release event was organized at the college auditorium of D.H.S.K College in association with Dr. R.K.B. Law College. In the event the book titled “Ai Mounotar Aboshan Houk” an assamese book authored by Anirbaan Dutta was released. The book was released by renowned author Dr Pranoy Phukan. Sahitya Academy Award winner Mr Gyan Pujari along with many other dignitaries attended the meeting as Guests of Honour. The event became a much enlightening one with the valuable speech of the dignitaries who discussed about the importance of literature and culture for the nation building and preservation of nationalism. The book indeed itself is a critique of the existing system of social order and the same was also critically analyzed by the dignitaries present in the meeting. The meeting was moderated by Dr Sashi Kanta Saikia, Principal of D.S.H.K College who concluded the meeting with a Formal Vote of Thanks.

Second Edition National Article Writing Competition

Competition

November 26, 2023:

The College decided to organize the Second Edition of the National Article Writing Competition, 2023 after witnessing the huge success of the First Edition. The Competition was opened for law students to discuss on the aspects of the Constitution of India since it was organized on the occasion of Constitution Day.

Framing of F.I.R. by the College

November 27, 2023:

The Legal Aid Cell of the College framed a F.I.R. on behalf of the cleaner of the college to be filed in the nearest Police Station. The victim and his family was receiving threatenings from strangers in their locality and for which they approached the Legal Aid Cell of the College who in return helped them by framing the F.I.R.

Career Counselling Programme on Future Prospects of Career in Law after 10+2

The first phase of the event was scheduled at Don Bosco School of Dibrugarh, Assam, where both the Faculties interacted with the students on the prospects of law as a career for them.

November 29, 2023: The College under the charge of Dr Deepankar Bhattacharjee and Mr Srimanta Bordoloi planned for organizing a series of counselling programmes in schools and colleges for creating an awareness amongst the students of Higher Secondary and Under Graduate Levels regarding the benefits of choosing law as a career.

One Week Online Faculty Development on Emerging Dimensions of Human Rights

December 10, 2023: The IQAC of the college organized a One Week Online Faculty Development Programme on Emerging Dimensions of Human Rights on the occasion of Human Rights Day from December 10 to December 16, 2023. Starting with the inaugural ceremony, the Chief Guest of Honour, Hon'ble Vice Chancellor of USTM, Meghalaya and Guest of Honour, Senior Advocate of Gauhati High Court inaugurated the FDP. In the FDP total 14 sessions were there on 14 different topics related to Human Rights. The FDP included topics ranging from Introduction to Human Rights; Armed Conflicts and Human Rights; International Humanitarian Law; Personal Law and Human Rights; Health Law and Human Rights; Human Rights of Disabled Persons; to Environmental Justice and Human Rights.

Many distinguished and intellectual personalities from across India chaired the sessions as Resource Persons including Prof. (Dr) Chintamani Rout, Former HoD Law Department, NEHU; Mr Shishir Tiwari, Assistant Professor, NEHU; Dr Balajinaika BG, Assistant Professor, Delhi University; Dr Gitanjali Ghosh, Associate Professor, Tezpur University; Mr Saheb Choudhury, Assistant Professor, NLU Assam; Dr Tanwi Shams, Assistant Professor, NLU Odisha; Prof. (Dr) Yugal Kishore, Former Professor & Vice Chancellor (O), NLU, Assam; Dr Girish KC and Dr Rangaswamy D, Assistant Professors, Karnataka State Law University; Mr Animesh Jha from Dharamashastra National Law University Dr Aman Kumar from Chanakya National Law University; Dr Anuja Mishra, Assistant Professor, Central University of South Bihar and Dr. P.R.L. Rajavanketasan from VIT Chennai. The FDP was moderated and arranged by Dr Jayanta Boruah and technically hosted by Dr Deepankar Bhattacharjee. In total 216 participants from across India registered for the event. The event came out to be a huge learning opportunity for the participants.

Release of Fortiori Reflecto

December 14, 2023: The college for the first time published its annual students' magazine by the name Fortiori Reflecto. The first volume was released at a Grand Inauguration Event organized by the college. It was attended by many dignitaries as Guest of Honours including Dr. Sashi Kanta Saikia, Principal, D.S.H.K. College; Smt. Reena Rani Bora; Head of the Department of Economics, Majuli College; Former Principal of Tinsukia

Law College; Faculty Representative from Nowgong Law College; and both the Principal and Former Vice Principal of the College. The magazine was released by Smt. Reena Rani Bora and she gave a brief analysis of the magazine. The Principal of D.S.H.L. College congratulated the success of the college in getting its first volume of the annual students' magazine published and announced to help the college financially in getting more copies printed by sponsoring an amount of INR: 10,000 on behalf of D.H.S.K. College. Smt. Bora in her inaugural speech briefly enumerated that how the magazine encompasses both creative and legal literature and covers geographical diversity from across India. She in her speech also appreciated the calligraphy of the title and the artistic works done by the students.

The student editors along with the Faculty-in-Charge were appreciated with formal letters of appreciation in the said event.

Release of Annual International Journal on Intellectual Property and Corporate Affairs (AIJIPCA)

December 14, 2023: On the same occasion, the first ever Volume of the Annual International Journal on Intellectual Property and Corporate Affairs (AIJIPCA) was released. The Principal of D.H.S.K. College released the journal and appreciated the success of the institution in bringing the journal in his enlightening speech. The journal is a joint commitment of Dr. R.K.B. Law College, Nowgong Law College, and Aequitas Victoria Foundation, Bihar. It has included special lectures of Justice Biplab Kumar Sarma and Veteran Academician Prof. (Dr.) M.K. Bhandari; scholarly

papers of authors from across India and Conference Proceeding of the National Conference on IPR and Corporate Affairs organized by the said three institutions in the year 2022. The inauguration of the journal was also attended by Mrs. Roselene Deori, Assistant Professor from Nowgong Law College.

Distribution of Appreciation Letters to the Students

December 14, 2023: In the same event appreciation letters were distributed amongst the students formally for performing in 2 Street Plays and also for working as Student Editors of the First Annual

Students' Magazine. The appreciation letters for the 2 street plays included those that they performed during the Non-Violence Day on October 01, 2023 and during the legal awareness programme at Dhaman Higher Secondary School on the occasion of National Legal Services Day on November 09, 2023. The appreciation letters for both the Street Plays were provided by the District Legal Services Authority (DLSA) Dibrugarh, Assam.

Mr R.K. Agarwalla taking Charge of Vice Principal

December 19, 2023: Mr. Rajkumar Agarwalla, a Senior Lecturer of the College took the charge as the Vice Principal on December 19, 2023. He has taken over the charge from Sr. Advocate Satyabrata Sarma. Mr Agarwalla has been dedicatedly serving the institution in all possible capabilities since a long time. His commitment to the institution has been well appreciated by offering the post and his occupying the chair of the Vice Principal is expected to bring new legacies in the growth of the institution.

One Week Online Faculty Development on Techniques and Methodology of Research for Social Sciences

December 20, 2023: Dr. R.K.B. Law College, Nowgong Law College and Kokrajhar Law College jointly organized a One Week Online Faculty Development Programme on Techniques and Methodology of Research for Social Sciences from December 20 to 26, 2023. At the inaugural ceremony, Prof. (Dr.) M.K. Bhandari attended as the Chief Guest of Honour, Prof. (Dr.) A. David Ambrose attended as the Guest of Honour and Prof. (Dr.) Arupjyoti Choudhury attended as the inaugurator of the FDP. All these dignitaries lighted the spirit of the FDP with their immense knowledge and vast experiences in the field of Research.

In the FDP there were around 21 technical sessions where eminent Resource Persons from across India and even from abroad chaired their respective sessions. The FDP dealt with vast areas of research including topics like introduction to research, problems faced in research, publication opportunities, literature review, methods and techniques of research, application of ICT Tools and SPSS and also research ethics and plagiarism. Resource Persons consisted of Renowned Academicists from Central Universities like North-Eastern Hill University, Central University of South Bihar, etc; State Universities like Cotton University, Karnataka State Law University, Osmania University, etc. leading foreign institutes like Jusfocus Institute of Research, The Netherlands and leading institutions from India like different National Law Universities, VIT Chennai, ILS Law School, etc. Around 90 participants from across the country registered and sincerely attended the event.

The valedictory session was enlightened by Prof. (Dr.) SC Roy, Professor, Chanakya National Law University as the Chief Guest of Honour and Dr. Kumari Nitu, Assistant Professor from Central University of South Bihar. The FDP was moderated by Dr Jayanta Boruah and technically hosted by Dr Deepankar Bhattacharjee. The FDP came to an end with the extension of the Formal Vote of Thanks by the Faculty Representative from Nowgong Law College.

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